

INTERNATIONAL LAW- OR RULES-BASED INTERNATIONAL ORDER? THE POLITICS OF INTERNATIONAL LAW IN COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVE

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The article analyses contemporary contestation over global order by distinguishing between an international law-based order (ILBO) and a rules-based international order (RBO). It argues that the post-2008 polycrises and the multipolarisation of the international community have weakened the institutional effectiveness of the liberal international order (LIO) and reopened the question of legitimate legality. The article compares the ILBO, anchored in sources doctrine, the Charter of the United Nations, and interpretative methods of international law, with the RBO as a broader and more politically interpretative framework. The comparison is organised around three criteria: normative structure, institutional infrastructure, and enforcement. The article then develops a comparative typology of state strategies and draws on Critical Legal Studies to understand international law as a field of political struggle. It concludes by developing strategic legalism as a way for small states to use international law relationally when managing power asymmetries within the international community.

Key words: comparative politics; international law-based order (ILBO); liberal international order (LIO); rules-based international order (RBO); strategic legalism.

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1 INTRODUCTION TO THE NORMATIVE QUESTION OF GLOBAL ORDER

“There is great disorder under the heavens; the situation is excellent,” Mao Zedong proclaimed in a very different historical context (Žižek 2021, 1). The first part of the statement still sounds strikingly relevant. The contemporary international community is marked by overlapping polycrises: the great recession and the long-term consequences of the financial crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic, growing social and global inequalities, accelerated climate and ecological collapse, renewed geopolitical confrontation, and large-scale armed conflicts, including the war in Ukraine and the atrocities in Gaza, where allegations of genocide have been raised in reports by the United Nations (UN) Special Rapporteur and in proceedings before the International Court of Justice (Albanese 2024a; Albanese 2024b; ICJ 2024a; ICJ 2024b; Albanese 2025a; Albanese 2025b).

These crises reinforce one another and reveal the structural weaknesses of the existing liberal international order (LIO) (Rutar, Hočevár and Lovéc 2023; cf. Volgy *et al.* 2009). Empirical estimates by the UN further confirm the depth of the disorder. The year 2022 saw the most active and intense armed conflicts since the end of the Cold War, and the upward trend continued in 2023 (Schulenburg 2023). Since 2008, interdependence has also become increasingly weaponised through supply chains, payment systems, energy and food politics, and the fragmentation of multilateral consensus (Farrell and Newman 2023). This reinforces the dispute over who may set the rules of global governance, and on what basis.

The ISPI² Report 2026 (Colombo and Magri 2026) sharpens this diagnosis by describing the present moment as a broader ‘free-for-all’, in which legal, diplomatic, and ethical constraints on international coexistence are increasingly weakened. Its introduction does not claim that international law has disappeared. Rather, it identifies the most acute crisis in the part of international law that regulates and restricts the use of force, while also highlighting the delegitimation of international institutions, the politicisation of trade and tariffs, the hollowing out of environmental governance, and the erosion of arms control arrangements.

Although the post-Cold War period was often described as “the end of history” (Fukuyama 1992), it is now clear that no universal consensus has been achieved. Instead, differences are deepening over sovereignty, human rights, trade fairness, and the legitimacy of the use of force. In a volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) environment, the LIO appears less as a consolidated constitutional architecture than as a historically conditioned configuration of power and norms. This raises the question of “critical junctures” (Acemoglu and Robinson 2012): does polycrisis create conditions for institutional transformation, or does it reinforce fragmentation and competition between rules?

History provides an instructive reminder. The proposition that commerce and economic interdependence pacify politics is often associated with Montesquieu’s (1748 [1748]) *doux commerce* tradition and was later reformulated by Angell (1909). Yet two world wars followed. Today’s world is even more interdependent, but conflicts persist and tensions are also escalating within

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states. Social inequalities, political polarisation, and the ‘crisis of representation’ reduce the ability to form stable domestic coalitions for multilateral cooperation (Piketty 2014; Streeck 2014). The question of global order is therefore both foreign and domestic. It concerns rules between states and the domestic conditions under which those rules are acceptable and enforceable.³

The dispute over order is often expressed through two phrases. The United States (US) and several Western allies refer to a “rules-based international order” (RBO), emphasising liberal values, democratic governance, and human rights. China and other rising powers increasingly stress an “international order based on international law”, or an international law-based order (ILBO), anchored in the UN Charter, sovereignty, and non-intervention (Cai 2023; *cf.* for a historical comparison Türk 1984). Many countries in the global South highlight historical inequalities, double standards, and selective enforcement of norms. Many non-Western states’ restrained response to the Russia–Ukraine war illustrates this legitimacy problem. While few states openly support Russia’s invasion, many reject the Western framing of the war as a straightforward defence of the RBO, as they associate this vocabulary with earlier Western violations of international law and selective enforcement (Narine 2023). The legal question is thus translated into a political one. Does legality mean codified, procedural law, or a broader set of ‘rules’ that may be defined by dominant coalitions?

Normative pluralism further complicates claims of universality (Avbelj 2018; Jaklič 2014). Competition between normative views is not an anomaly but a constant feature of international life. Henrich (2020, 3) shows that Western, educated, industrialised, rich, and democratic (WEIRD) societies are globally unrepresentative in many institutional and psychological characteristics and are often “total outliers”. This does not invalidate the universalist tendencies of international law, but it does caution against assuming cultural neutrality. For this reason, the central question becomes which rules are sufficiently precise and procedurally anchored to function as a shared legal denominator across legal-cultural differences.

Crucially, ILBO and RBO are not merely analytical categories, but are part of political practice. Naming an order is also a proposal for a criterion of legitimacy. ILBO implies the primacy of the UN Charter, formal sources of international law, and sovereign equality, while RBO often includes a value-ideological framework in which certain ‘rules’ are presented as a condition for legitimate membership in the international community. This tension becomes more acute in crises that require swift action, such as the use of force, sanctions, pandemic management, and responses to climate disasters. In such situations, references to ‘rules’ are often intertwined with pragmatic action justified by necessity. The distinction between legally binding obligations and political standards is therefore not a matter of formalism, but a question of limiting arbitrariness.

The existing literature can be grouped into four broad approaches (Hafner-Burton, Victor and Lupu 2012). Doctrinal international law scholarship examines sources, hierarchy, interpretation, and compliance (Crawford 2019). Liberal-institutionalist and constructivist approaches emphasise institutionalisation, norm dynamics, and legitimacy (Finnemore and Sikkink 1998; Ikenberry 2011). Realist and international political-economy approach stress hegemony,

³ Putnam’s (1988) model of two-level games shows that the legality of foreign policy is not only systemic, but also domestic. Institutional veto actors, public opinion and coalitions of interest also shape whether a state ratifies a treaty, accepts the jurisdiction of a court, or implements sanctions.

structural power, and material dependence (Strange 1988; Guzzini 1993). Critical Legal Studies (CLS) and Third World Approaches to International Law (TWAIL) highlight indeterminacy, colonial legacies, and distributional asymmetries (Koskenniemi 1990; Anghie 2005; Koskenniemi 2005).

Related debates have also appeared in the *Journal of Comparative Politics* (JoCP). Earlier JoCP contributions examined how multipolarisation, hegemonic change and regional foreign-policy positioning affect the strategies of states in international politics (Udovič 2011; Tamene 2013). Other articles addressed the renewed relevance of demands for a more equitable global economic order (Svetličič 2022b) and the domestic consequences of crisis and autocratisation in East-Central Europe (Ágh 2022). More recent JCP work further shows how small states operate within EU foreign-policy procedures, how courts can structure political coordination through legal reasoning, and how security dependence may produce divergent strategies among otherwise comparable Central European actors (Rechtik and Mareš 2021; Fazekas 2024; Udovič and Žipaj 2025). This article builds on these debates but shifts the focus to the legal-political vocabulary through which global order is justified, contested and strategically mobilised. It therefore connects comparative politics with international legal doctrine and global political economy by analysing the contest between ILBO and RBO.

The article's originality lies in connecting these strands through a single comparative design. The comparative perspective is twofold: it compares the legal and political architectures of ILBO and RBO, and it compares how selected states, international organisations and institutions mobilise these vocabularies in practice. What remains less developed in the literature is precisely this link between a doctrinal comparison of the two vocabularies and a comparative typology of state strategies.

The article does not address this dilemma solely from the perspective of international legal scholarship but develops two interrelated arguments. First, the differences between ILBO and RBO cannot be understood abstractly, because states, international organisations and institutions strategically interpret and apply legality. Their behaviour differs systematically according to their position of power in the global political economy, historical experiences and internal political constraints. Second, drawing primarily on CLS and critical international theory, the article argues that neither ILBO nor RBO operates outside power relations. International law is not an apolitical constraint, but a structured field in which power is translated into demands for universality (Koskenniemi 1990; Koskenniemi 2005). In this environment, the position of small and less powerful states becomes particularly important. As Long (2022) demonstrates, even relationally small states can exert (conditional) influence through institutional levers, coalitions and the mobilisation of strategic norms, but such strategies are highly dependent on the degree of codification, institutionalisation and procedural anchoring of legality.

To reinforce or weaken and thus refine these theses, the article methodologically combines: (i) a doctrinal analysis of sources and interpretations of international law; (ii) an analysis of the global political economy as a material framework of contestation; and (iii) a comparative analysis of state practices and discourses. This combination understands international law as a real but contingent moment in a broader historical process (Sinclair 2021). It rests on the ontological assumption that the global order is constituted by real legal, economic and political structures that function as generative mechanisms (Brglez 2008; Kurki and Sinclair 2010; Lovec 2013). Epistemologically, it rejects both the reduction

of international law to ideology or mere discourse and the normative absolutisation of international law. The following sections develop the argument in sequence: from multipolarisation and the political-economic foundations of contestation to the doctrinal reconstruction of ILBO, the conceptual analysis of RBO, a comparative typology of state strategies, critical legal perspectives and approaches to strategic legalism.

2 FROM LIO TO MULTIPOLAR CONFLICT

After 1945, the LIO combined security arrangements, trade liberalisation, and institutionalised cooperation. The crisis of liberal internationalism is therefore not only a crisis of power transition, but also a crisis in the relationship between liberal principles and the institutional practices of the LIO itself (Lovec and Svetličič 2019). After 1990, the unipolar moment enabled the expansion of liberal norms and consolidated asymmetric interpretative authority. It fostered a Fukuyamian (1992) illusion: that the ideological “end of history” and the apparent absence of a systemic economic alternative after the collapse of state socialism would result in a stable LIO.

The order operated as ‘open’ and inclusive (Ikenberry 2011), but its practical stability was inseparable from the material hegemony of the US and its capacity to support institutions with security and financial resources (Gilpin 1987). This unipolar configuration reinforced the belief that liberal norms could be enforced even without strict consensus in the Security Council (Slaughter 1997).

Debates on Kosovo, Iraq, and later Libya turned this belief into a tension between the classic interpretation of the prohibition of the use of force and arguments about ‘humanitarian intervention’ or the responsibility to protect (R2P; Sancin and Kovič Dine 2023). Doctrines for the protection of civilians are also being developed within ILBO. The key dilemma remains the threshold of necessity, the bearer of judgement, and responsibility for the consequences. This leaves room for accusations of selectivity and for subsequent references to RBO as a political framework that should supplement or ‘update’ international law with value standards. This legitimacy deficit is particularly evident in non-Western responses to the Russia–Ukraine war. Narine (2023; *cf.* Forsberg and Patomäki 2023) argues that Western references to RBO are weakened by the memory of Iraq, Kosovo, Afghanistan, and Libya, which many non-Western actors regard as evidence that the West invokes rules selectively while violating international law when its own strategic preferences require it.

Here the ISPI diagnosis of “de-constitutionalisation” strengthens the argument. De Sena and Mauri (2026) argue that the contemporary problem is not the disappearance of all international legal rules, as many treaty regimes continue to function in ordinary practice. The specific issue is the weakening of the constitutional layer of the post-1945 order: the prohibition of the threat or use of force, self-determination, and fundamental human rights constraints no longer discipline political practice with the same authority. This formulation supports the distinction developed here: ILBO remains doctrinally structured, but its higher-order constraints are increasingly bypassed or reinterpreted through political necessity, coalition practice, and strategic discretion.

At the same time, asymmetries in global governance have become entrenched (Popović and Štajner 1981; Simoniti 1989; Gilman 2015; Svetličič 2022a; Svetličič 2022b). The Bretton Woods institutions, trade regime, and security

arrangements functioned as the infrastructure of order, but their policies were often perceived as disciplinary. Fiscal conditions, liberalisation packages, and standards of 'good governance' were linked to the preferences of the dominant economies. RBO can therefore also be understood as a hierarchical order in which authority is unevenly distributed (Lake 2009). Unsurprisingly that part of the global South has remained ambivalent towards the 'rules'. It accepted universality as protection, but at the same time experienced inequality in implementation, which gradually undermined the legitimacy of a unified understanding of order.

After 2008, the role of economics in geopolitics became more pronounced, as disintegration tendencies in the global political economy translated into exits, conflicts, and competing institutional projects (Patomäki 2008; Patomäki 2018; Patomäki 2022). The financial crisis made part of the neoliberal project appear less legitimate and accelerated the use of geo-economic tools: sanctions, technological restrictions, investment controls, and 'security' exceptions in trade. Trade, investment, and finance rules were increasingly treated as instruments of strategic competition rather than as neutral rules of the game (Strange 1988; Cohen 2008).

This shift is legally relevant because it raises the question of whether such instruments remain within ILBO – contractual or treaty law, with clearly defined exceptions and adjudication – or become part of the broader RBO, where 'rules' may be consistent with international law without being legally binding and may be enforced through coalitions, network power and pressure (Farrell and Newman 2019; Jorgensen 2021). At the same time, contradictions within ILBO deepened after 2001. The security agenda reinforced practices of exceptionalism and selective legality, especially in the context of the global war on terror (Hajjar 2019), while the economic agenda intensified internal inequalities through disciplinary neoliberal reforms (Gill 1995; Piketty 2014; Streeck 2014; Patomäki 2018; Patomäki 2022).

Growing inequality and the 'winners' and 'losers' of globalisation have strengthened populist politics and reduced support for multilateral compromises (Banerjee and Duflo 2019). As a result, domestic politics has increasingly determined the extent to which governments can, or are willing to, respect international commitments (Putnam 1988).

Multipolarisation – the rise of China, the strengthening of BRICS⁴ and the relative decline of Western hegemony – therefore means more than a redistribution of material capacities; it also rearticulates legitimacy (Arbeiter 2020; Fister 2021). Some emerging actors are betting on reforming existing institutions, especially trade and financial ones. Others are building parallel instruments. The debate on the future of global governance is thus overshadowed by the question of whether the dispute will be conducted within a shared legal denominator or through a competition of discourses and coalitions.

Rachman (2023) describes this shift as a transition to a period in which the 'weight' of the great powers is once again translated into open rivalry. In the absence of a single hegemon capable of stabilising interpretation, interpretative centres multiply. Competing legal and political languages then increase the risk of normative inflation and disputes over who speaks for the 'rules'. These languages are not merely discursive. They are usually grounded in structural

⁴ BRICS is an international intergovernmental organisation named after its first (and most important) members: Brazil, the Russian Federation, India, China and South Africa.

power in finance, technology and supply chains, where dependencies are most easily translated into pressure and 'rules'. The next section therefore shows how the global political economy functions as the material axis that feeds the normative dispute between ILBO and RBO.

3 THE GLOBAL POLITICAL ECONOMY AS A STRUCTURE OF NORMATIVE CONFLICT

The dispute over who defines the 'rules' is clearest in the global political economy. Power is often structural and derives from the ability to shape the frameworks within which others make decisions (Strange 1988; Guzzini 1993). In the monetary and financial sphere, currencies, payment systems and credit regimes are not merely technical instruments, but sources of political influence (Cohen 2008). The dollar, access to liquidity, correspondent banking, clearing systems and digital platforms enable sanctions and exclusions with real distributional consequences. Digitalisation strengthens this mechanism because payment infrastructures, cloud services and platform ecosystems transform economic dependencies into political leverage and, ultimately, political conflicts (Cohen 2008; Farrell and Newman 2023).

The question is whether such measures are justified as legally enshrined in the UN Charter or as coalition practice legitimised by the RBO. This is also evident in the EU's attempt to preserve actorness under the weakening LIO, especially in trade, digital sovereignty and conflict resolution, where legal-institutional commitments are increasingly combined with strategic autonomy and regulatory power (Bojinović Fenko and Brsakovska Bazerkoska 2025).

In the era of global value chains, interdependence often becomes dependency. Concentrated supply chains, restricted access to semiconductors or energy resources, and jurisdictionally controlled payment systems create opportunities for 'security' exceptions and exert pressure. Rodrik (2011) warns that globalisation without political compromise produces a trilemma between democracy, national sovereignty, and hyperglobalisation. When compromise fails, states turn to instruments enabled by structural power. The weakening of global value chains, together with nearshoring, friend-shoring and regionalisation, further reinforces deglobalisation and fragmentation, multiplying the arenas in which ILBO and RBO are contested.

The climate, ecological and social crises further strain normative frameworks. Moore (2015) demonstrates that capitalism has historically relied on 'cheap nature', so the transition to a low-carbon economy raises not only technological and financial issues but also disputes over rules and burden sharing. These disputes are inseparable from social inequalities, democratic backsliding, and the radicalisation of domestic conflicts. Chang (2020) advocates pro-development multilateralism, which is only possible if the rules consider development needs and distributive justice.

Digital transformation adds a third layer of conflict. Rules on data, artificial intelligence, and platforms are often established outside traditional treaties: through standards, codes, interoperability regimes, and regulatory dialogues. Zuboff (2018) analyses data as a key resource of surveillance capitalism, while Jorgensen (2021) warns that digital infrastructures create new forms of dependency. Technological giants can thus produce quasi-feudal dependencies among platforms, states, firms, and users, a dynamic that resonates with

Wagenknecht's broader economic conception of neofeudal capitalism (Varoufakis 2023; *cf.* Wagenknecht 2017).

As a result, disputes over 'rules' are increasingly occurring through standardisation bodies, platform policies, and transgovernmental networks. Such rules can be effective, but they have a different legitimacy profile. ILBO emphasises formal sources, while RBO often refers to 'best practices' and the standards of technology and regulatory centres. This shifts the question of legality to one of access to standardisation and democratic accountability.

The ISPI Report 2026 provides concrete examples of this shift across various issue areas. In trade, the move towards politicised tariffs, export controls, regionalisation, and plurilateral arrangements shows how the multilateral legal system is increasingly supplemented – and sometimes displaced – by instruments of strategic competition (Tajoli 2026). In finance, digitalisation, payment systems, and confidence in the dollar demonstrate that apparently technical infrastructures can become vectors of systemic power and vulnerability (Bruni 2026). In artificial intelligence and space, the problem is even clearer: regulatory authority emerges through standards, infrastructure, platforms, procurement and public-private ecosystems rather than classical treaty-making (Aresu 2026; Iacomino 2026). These cases show the ILBO/RBO distinction is not limited to security law. It also structures the material governance of interdependence.

The financial crisis also demonstrated that liberalisation and financial innovation bring not only growth but also fragility and redistribution. Krippner (2011) describes the financial 'reorientation' of countries, Streeck (2014) the crisis of democratic capitalism, and Piketty (2014) the concentration of wealth as a source of political delegitimization of compromises. These tensions are then projected into foreign policy disputes over rules. In a longer-term perspective, Arrighi (1994) and Wallerstein (2004) point out that hegemonies change along with transformations of accumulation regimes, while Gill (1995), Gilman (2015), and Svetličič (2021; 2022a) show that distributive issues, from NIEO⁵ to today's reform demands, are returning as the axis of legitimacy of global governance.

As disputes over 'rules' materialise through financial, climate and digital dependencies, the next step is to show how ILBO institutionally produces, interprets and enforces legality.

4 THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE ILBO

When disputes over 'rules' arise through financial, climate and digital dependencies, ILBO typically channels them through formal sources, interpretative rules, and institutional enforcement mechanisms. The legal order comprises formal and informal institutions, ranging from contracts, courts, and sanctions to taboos, customs, and codes of conduct. Formal rules can be changed relatively quickly, whereas informal rules often serve as slower cultural and political constraints (Hirsch 2017). In practice, the two levels are intertwined: law is based on social practices, and social practices can gradually be codified.⁶

⁵ Declaration on the New International Economic Order was adopted in the UN General Assembly on 1 May 1974.

⁶ Traditional International Relations theory has understood international regimes as sets of principles, norms, rules and decision-making procedures around which actors' expectations converge in specific issue areas (Krasner 1982). The influence of social constructivism and the

In this sense, ILBO is not only a text but an institutional and practical infrastructure of the global order.

The understanding of international law increasingly extends beyond classical, purely contractual logic (Cohen 2012). Part of the literature refers to constitutionalisation: the gradual emergence of hierarchies of norms (*jus cogens*), institutional mechanisms of interpretation, and the spread of *erga omnes* obligations (Klabbers, Peters and Ulfstein 2009; cf. Zidar 2009). At the same time, empirical research relativises purely instrumentalist interpretations. Simmons (2009) shows that international legal commitments can mobilise domestic actors, courts, and civil society, thereby increasing compliance even without central coercion. Sceptics, however, argue that compliance often reflects a coincidence between law and interests. Goldsmith and Posner (2005) therefore view international law as a product of rational calculation and repeated interactions.

For analysing ILBO, it is useful to distinguish three levels: (i) the normative structure (sources, hierarchy, interpretation); (ii) the institutional infrastructure (courts, international organisations, control mechanisms); and (iii) enforcement (ranging from diplomatic practice and reciprocity to sanctions). The same three criteria are used also in the following section to evaluate RBO, which makes the comparison between ILBO and RBO explicit. ILBO is relatively strongest at the first level because it offers a clearer doctrine of what counts as law and more stable rules of interpretation.

ILBO is based on a structured doctrine of sources.⁷ Article 38(1) of the Statute of the International Court of Justice (United Nations 1945) defines the main sources of international law. International treaties, customary international law and general principles of law are the primary formal sources that may create new rules of international law. Some authors (Degan 2011, 189–203; Corten *et al.* 2019, 359–369) would also include certain unilateral international legal acts of states, such as promises, recognitions, protests, certain statements or declarations, and waivers or renunciations of rights, while others treat these acts separately (Zupančič 2013; Türk 2015, 188–191; Crawford 2019, 401–408). Judicial decisions and legal scholarship are classified as subsidiary means. They do not create new rules, but they can have a decisive influence on which interpretation prevails as convincing.

The model of norm production is, as a rule, consensual. States become bound by ratifying treaties or by contributing to the formation of customary international law, which consists of state practice and *opinio juris*. In disputes about custom, the burden of proof, the uniformity of practice and the status of the persistent objector are often decisive. General principles of law, such as *bona fide*, *lex specialis*, *lex posterior* and the prohibition of abuse of rights, act as a bridge between fragmented issue areas of international law and have historically enabled legal gaps to be filled.

A key advantage of ILBO is the argumentative discipline of interpretation. The Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (United Nations 1969) sets out

“practical turn” has shifted attention to the contested emergence, diffusion and implementation of norms through normative cycles (Adler and Pouliot 2011; Pouliot 2016; Peez 2022). This approach emphasises the dynamic and often conflictual processes through which norms are constructed, negotiated and institutionalised in world politics (Peter and Brglez 2007).

⁷ Koskenniemi (2005, 562–617) points out that the ‘internal’ view of international lawyers stems either from the doctrine of sources or from the sovereign equality of states. Regardless of the point of departure, both perspectives lead to the relative autonomy of International Law in relation to other social sciences and disciplines.

common rules of interpretation in Articles 31–33, limiting arbitrary readings and allowing reference to the text, context, subsequent practice and other relevant rules of international law.⁸ In practice, ILBO is often supplemented by soft law, including declarations, guidelines and resolutions, which is not binding in itself but may influence the formation of customary law or the interpretation of treaties. It is important to note that soft law in ILBO generally serves as a supplement to formal sources, not as a substitute for them. This preserves the distinction between the legal and the political.

The normative basis of ILBO remains the Charter of the UN (United Nations 1945). Article 2(1) codifies the sovereign equality of states, Article 2(4) the prohibition of the threat or use of force, and Article 2(3) the duty to settle disputes peacefully. The classic exceptions to the prohibition of the threat or use of force are individual and collective self-defence (Article 51) and collective security measures under Chapter VII. The prohibition of aggression and, more broadly, the prohibition of the threat or use of force are also established as norms of customary international law. Much of the literature emphasises their peremptory or cogent character (*jus cogens*). However, debates on humanitarian intervention, preventive self-defence and R2P show that interpretative politics also opens within ILBO. Legal arguments about necessity, inevitability, proportionality and collective legitimacy are accompanied by questions of selectivity and distributive costs.

The network of human rights and international humanitarian law standards is also important. The two 1966 Covenants (in force from 1976), one on civil and political rights and the other on economic, social and cultural rights, together with regional systems such as the 1950 European Convention on Human Rights and its (16) protocols, and the four 1949 Geneva Conventions on the protection of victims of war, supplemented by the two 1977 Additional Protocols on international and non-international armed conflicts, codify standards that have become central to legitimacy expectations. This is where ILBO and RBO often overlap. Principles of humanity may function as legal obligations, while standards and exceptions based on military necessity are sometimes applied selectively in practice. For credibility, it is therefore crucial that value standards refer to formal sources and enforcement procedures.

ILBO is not merely a horizontal system of mutual obligations. Article 53 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties recognises *jus cogens* norms from which no derogation is permitted, while *erga omnes* obligations are developed in other instruments and case law. Secondary rules on state responsibility in the draft Articles on Responsibility of States for Internationally Wrongful Acts (International Law Commission 2001) – now practically in the status of customary international law – determine when an unlawful act occurs, what the consequences are and what forms of countermeasures are permitted. The draft

⁸ Under Article 31 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, treaties must be interpreted in good faith, in accordance with the ordinary meaning of their terms, in their context and considering their object and purpose. The preamble and annexes, as well as related agreements and instruments adopted at the time of conclusion, must also be considered. Interpretation must further consider subsequent agreements, subsequent practice in the application of the treaty among the parties, and other relevant rules of international law. Article 32 allows recourse to supplementary means of interpretation, including the *travaux préparatoires*, to clarify the meaning of a provision or confirm the parties' historical intent. In practice, as illustrated by the Court of Justice of the European Union, teleological interpretation may, where the object and purpose are clearly defined, also extend beyond a strictly textual reading. Article 33 requires that all authenticated language versions be considered when interpreting a treaty.

thus serves as a reference framework for argumentation and limits what can be presented as a legitimate countermeasure.

Jus cogens has two key functions: (i) it delegitimises certain practices regardless of the consent of individual states, and (ii) it creates an argument that transcends reciprocity. This is evident in the prohibition of aggression, genocide, slavery, torture, racial discrimination and apartheid, as well as in the duty not to recognise an illegal situation resulting from such international crimes. However, the problem of enforcement remains here too. *Jus cogens* is a powerful legal argument that can reinforce coalition pressure, but it cannot replace political will on its own. Another important element of the hierarchy is the primacy of the UN Charter over other treaty obligations (Article 103 of the UN Charter), which in practice raises dilemmas when sanctions regimes, security measures and human rights overlap.

Institutionally, ILBO includes courts and arbitration tribunals. The International Court of Justice (ICJ) remains the central forum, although its binding jurisdiction generally depends on the consent of states. Nevertheless, ICJ advisory opinions can strengthen argumentative pressure (Paulson 2004). In the economic sphere, the World Trade Organization (WTO) dispute settlement mechanism has long been among the most judicialized legal regimes, but the paralysis of the Appellate Body reveals the political conditioning of enforcement (Hopewell 2016). The Multi-Party *Interim* Appeal Arbitration Arrangement (MPIA), established in 2020, partially mitigates this problem for participating WTO members but does not replace a universal appellate mechanism (Council of the European Union 2020). Similarly, in investment arbitration – whether through Investor-State Dispute Settlement or an Investment Court System – disputes arise over the relationship between investment protection, public regulatory space and democratic legitimacy (Llamzon 2007). International criminal law is a formally developed but politically controversial case. Not all states recognise the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (ICC), and some actors reject or resist its jurisdiction, reducing its universality and reinforcing accusations of selectivity.

More broadly, ILBO operates through several compliance mechanisms: monitoring, reporting, ‘naming and shaming’, and internal implementation through courts and legislative reforms. Simmons (2009) shows that legal effects often materialise domestically, where domestic actors are activated. This dimension is also important for small(er) states if it strengthens their legitimacy capital and increases their credibility when demanding respect for international law externally.

ILBO’s greatest vulnerability is its enforcement deficit. In the absence of a world government (*cf.* Patomäki 2023), global governance institutions have limited power to enforce compliance. Even when international law is clear, sanctions and coercion are fragmented and politically conditioned. The Security Council can, in theory, enforce ICJ judgments (Article 94(2) of the UN Charter), but in practice this does not happen. Instead of automatic coercion, mechanisms of reciprocity, reputation, economic dependence and coalition pressure operate (Guzman 2008).

Another limitation is the built-in institutional hierarchy. The Security Council institutionalises inequality through permanent members and veto power, which affects the use of collective security mechanisms. At the same time, the global legal order also faces fragmentation. The constitutionalisation perspective emphasises the development of *jus cogens* and the strengthening of judicial institutions, while the pluralist perspective points to the dispersion and overlap

of legal regimes (Krisch 2010). In its report on fragmentation, the International Law Commission (2006) highlighted conflicts of norms and jurisdictions and the dynamics of “forum shopping” (Helfer 2004). Recent work on regime complexity and refugee rights similarly shows that international cooperation often takes place at the intersection of overlapping regimes, where legal protection depends on the interaction between different normative frameworks (Hedžet 2025).

This combination of high normative discipline and weak, politically conditioned enforcement creates a space in which ‘rules’ often begin to take effect outside formal sources. This is the key transition to RBO.

5 RBO: POLITICAL NORMATIVITY AND INTERPRETATIVE AUTHORITY

The previous section presented ILBO as a framework that stabilises legality through sources doctrine and interpretative rules. RBO is primarily a political-discursive construct. The term “rules-based international order” does not appear in the UN Charter, the ICJ Statute (United Nations 1945) or the core universal conventions. RBO refers to a desired way of conducting international relations, in which rules may range from binding legal norms to soft standards and political commitments.⁹ Scott (2018) therefore points out that RBO vocabulary often signals a shift from the idea of international law as a relatively autonomous ideal to a more explicitly political articulation of normativity. The following analysis mirrors the ILBO section through the same three criteria: normative structure, institutional infrastructure and enforcement.

The conceptual ambiguity of RBO brings both flexibility and interpretative openness. In terms of normative structure, RBO lacks an agreed doctrine of sources and often combines treaty law, customary law, soft law and politically articulated standards into a single framework. In terms of institutional infrastructure, authority is less centred on universal legal institutions and more dispersed among coalitions, regulatory networks, standard-setting bodies and dominant market or platform actors. In terms of enforcement, RBO relies more on coalition pressure, sanctions, market access and reputational costs than on adjudication. This does not make RBO irrelevant. It means that its legitimacy depends on transparency, consistency and possible impartial review. Talmon (2019) points out that RBO can blur the distinction between binding and non-binding rules and create an impression of universality where political coalition normativity is at stake. Soft law can increase responsiveness, but it is generally more dependent on the interests of politically influential actors (Hafner 2003) and can lead to ‘rule inflation’. Vylegzhanin *et al.* (2021) therefore question whether the ‘rules’ in RBO reflect international law or national preferences.

The main difference between ILBO and RBO is interpretative authority. In ILBO, interpretation is based on recognised sources and codified interpretative rules, while in RBO it is often established through political statements, coalition

⁹ To prevent interdisciplinary disputes between International Relations and International Law scholars from obscuring the differences between ILBO and RBO (Koskenniemi 2009), it is useful to distinguish between legal norms and social norms. In the interactional theory of international law, legal norms must not only be socially widespread but must also satisfy the criteria of legality – generality, clarity, accessibility, predictability and consistency with the conduct of officials – which enable the “practice of legality” (Brunnée and Toope 2010; Brunnée and Toope 2017). Law is thus not merely discourse, but an institutionally sustained behavioural pattern that generates a constitutive sense of obligation and legitimacy.

practice and selective institutional support. Mearsheimer (2001) points out that order often reflects power relations, and that this connection can be obscured in RBO discourse by the rhetoric of 'the rule of law'. Selective compliance is particularly evident where rules constrain key preferences (*e.g.*, blocking the WTO Appellate Body, resisting the ICC, or imposing sanctions without broad multilateral consensus). Legality is emphasised when it legitimises preferences and relativised when it restricts them, so RBO can act as a legitimising vocabulary of hierarchy and hegemony.

It is necessary to distinguish between the principle of the rule of law and RBO. The rule of law means the subordination of authority to established legal norms and procedures that limit arbitrariness (Bishop 1961). If RBO is equated with the rule of law, the distinction between legally binding obligations and political standards is blurred. The 'rule' articulated by a strong coalition can take on the appearance of universal legality. ILBO at least argumentatively limits the arbitrary redefinition of rules through sources and interpretation, while RBO, without clear sources and procedures, risks becoming a set of politically contingent 'rules'.

The legitimacy of RBO depends primarily on consistency and distributive justice. If the 'rules' systematically create advantages for developed economies, inequalities are reinforced and political divisions deepen. The global South therefore often perceives RBO as a framework in which double standards are more easily legitimised (Chang 2020). The problem is not merely conceptual ambiguity, but credibility. Narine (2023) shows that many non-Western states interpret Western appeals to RBO through the memory of post-Cold War Western interventions and therefore view RBO less as a neutral legal-political order than as a selective vocabulary of Western authority.

The value dimension adds another complication. The RBO is often associated with liberal-democratic values and human rights, but without a clear legal source, it risks slipping from legal debate into 'civilisational' politics. Vrečko Ilc and Šabič (2021) warn that such references can be used to strategically advance interests and discursively delegitimise opponents. Therefore, the question is not only whether the rule exists, but who defines it and who benefits from it.

RBO discourse is particularly influential in geo-economic policies. Export controls, foreign investment restrictions, sanctions and 'security' exceptions are often justified by the protection of 'rules' and 'values', but in practice they combine legal elements with political standards, such as 'responsible supply chains' and 'reliable partners' (Chatham House 2015). Since such rules are often insufficiently specific, the risk of arbitrariness increases, as does the possibility that they become tools of competition (Nahtigal 2023). At the same time, China also refers to the RBO in certain contexts, emphasising sovereignty, development and non-discrimination. This confirms that the dispute is often not about the idea of order itself, but about the content of the rules and who interprets them (Walt 2021; Rodrik and Walt 2024).

In practice, the RBO can complement the ILBO when the 'rules' are clearly enshrined in treaties, customary law or transparent procedures of international organisations. In such cases, it can increase effectiveness. However, when rules are enforced primarily through coalition practice without a clear legal basis and without the possibility of impartial interpretation, the RBO risks legitimising selectivity. The normative challenge of the future order therefore lies in mechanisms that restore procedural accountability to the RBO.

This conceptual openness translates into differences in state practice. The next section therefore shows how states use legality as a political resource and how their strategies differ in terms of discourse, behaviour and institutional preferences.

6 COMPARATIVE STATE STRATEGIES: LEGALITY AS A SHIELD AND AN INSTRUMENT

The distinction between ILBO and RBO becomes fully meaningful only against the actual practices of states. Order is not merely a normative framework, but the outcome of selective interpretations, institutional preferences, and strategic decisions under conditions of asymmetric power. Rather than a binary of compliance and violation, the article examines how states use legality as a political resource: when they invoke it, reinterpret it, and circumvent it. The comparison considers three dimensions: (1) discursive orientation, (2) practical behaviour, and (3) institutional preferences. The typology in Table 1 is based on the expanded discursive evidence from the Appendix (Table A2),¹⁰ which codes the presence or absence of key terms (RBO/ILBO; UN/UN Charter; rule of law) and extracts representative sentence anchors (predominant and most prominent). The coding is deliberately light: it does not replace a full corpus analysis, but it enables a consistent synthesis of the four ideal-typical strategies. On this basis, Table 1 summarises four ideal-type strategies as recurring combinations of discourse, institutional preferences, and behaviour.

TABLE 1: COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY OF COUNTRIES' APPROACHES TO ILBO AND RBO

Type of actor	Typical representatives	Dominant discourse	Practical behaviour	Implications for order
Liberal-hegemonic	US (partly United Kingdom)	RBO, liberal values, rule of law	Selective application of international law; instrumental use of institutions (e.g., WTO, ICC)	Normative flexibility; erosion of universality
Normative multilateralists	EU, Canada, smaller European countries	International law as the basis of order	High formal compliance; reliance on adjudication; limited executive power	ILBO as protection, but structural vulnerability
Revisionist legalists	China (partly Russia)	International legal order, sovereignty, UN Charter	Formal support for ILBO; restrictive interpretation; resistance to normative conditioning	Reinterpretation of sovereignty; fragmentation of norms
Pragmatic actors of the global South	Countries of Africa, Asia, Latin America	Sovereignty, distributive justice	Forum shopping; selective institutional commitments	Pluralisation of normative centres

Source: author's own elaboration, based on the documents listed in the Appendix (Table A2).¹¹

¹⁰ The empirical corpus of public official documents used for the Appendix is deposited in *Zenodo* (Brglez 2026c). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20304876.

¹¹ Recent strategic texts used in the Appendix (Table A2) and deposited in *Zenodo* (Brglez 2026c) do not fall into a simple legal/non-legal binary. They may also be read as a continuum from the UN-centred legal multilateralism, through value-based coalition order, towards open national-interest balancing. The 2022 US, EU and NATO documents still present RBO as at least partly compatible with the UN Charter and international law, whereas the 2025-2026 US strategic documents move the vocabulary towards sovereignty, burden-shifting, balance of power and military-industrial capacity. This confirms the article's central warning: RBO can be re-anchored

The liberal-hegemonic ideal type is grounded in RBO, presenting liberal values, including democracy, human rights and open markets, as an integral part of the 'rules', while commitment to institutions is often conditional in practice. Mechanisms such as the WTO and ICC are supported when they reinforce expectations *vis-à-vis* others and restricted when they reduce one's own discretion. Instrumentality is also evident in the use of sanctions, references to 'security' exceptions and emphasis on 'coalitions of the willing'. When rules are enforced through coalition pressure rather than broad multilateral consensus, RBO acts as a legitimising framework that undermines the universality of ILBO and reinforces perceptions of double standards in the global South (Scott 2018).

Normative multilateralists build their identity around formal commitment to ILBO: ratification, support for courts and emphasis on procedural legality. A typical example is the European Union (EU), where legal institutionalism is part of the internal constitution (Kelemen 2011). For normative multilateralists, international law is a key safeguard against arbitrariness, but the approach is structurally vulnerable because of limited executive power. International courts clearly depend on the legitimacy and cooperation of major actors, so this type must complement legal commitment with coalition strategy and support for reforms that increase the effectiveness of enforcement (Dunoff and Pollack 2017). The Central European position is especially important because it cannot be reduced to simple rule-taking. The failed-socialisation narrative surrounding Central Europe shows how regional actors may be normatively positioned, labelled and disciplined within broader liberal institutional frameworks (Lovec, Kočí and Šabič 2021).

Revisionist 'legalists' generally defend the international legal order and refer to the UN Charter (sovereignty, non-intervention, non-discrimination), while rejecting liberal normative conditioning and attempts to make value standards function as universal obligations. China's argument often combines formal legality with plurality of modernisation paths (Cai 2023). In practice, the formal language of law can be intertwined with a restrictive interpretation of its scope in 'core' interests of sovereignty and resistance to external control. This can also reinforce 'authoritarian international law' that supports regime security without accepting liberal rights as universal obligations (Biddulph, Cooney and Zhu 2012; Ginsburg 2014; DeLisle 2024).

Pragmatic actors in the global South are a heterogeneous group focused on maximising development space. In discourse, they emphasise sovereignty and redistributive justice, but they combine ILBO and RBO in practice. The restrained response of many non-Western states to the Russia-Ukraine war confirms this pragmatism. Narine (2023) argues that these states do not necessarily support Russia's invasion, but many refuse to subordinate their own economic and strategic interests to a Western RBO narrative that they regard as historically selective. When law acts as a protection against arbitrariness, for example through non-discrimination, development exceptions or protection against the unlawful use of force, they invoke it. When international legal regimes reproduce inequalities, they use forum shopping and parallel coalitions, as seen in climate negotiations, debt debates, trade disputes and demands for financial institution reform (Rajagopal 2013; Acharya 2014; Gilman 2015; Chang 2020; Svetličič 2022a; De Sena and Mauri 2026).

in ILBO, but it can also drift towards post-RBO (illiberal) power politics when 'rules' lose legal traceability and procedural contestability.

The typology confirms that ILBO and RBO are overlapping frameworks that states use according to their position of power and domestic politics. Norm contestation is therefore not necessarily destructive; it may also lead to the adaptation and modernisation of norms (Deitelhoff and Zimmermann 2019). The key question is whether transformation takes place within a shared legal denominator or slips into a fragmented discourse of rules, where authority depends on political superiority. China's position shows formal anchoring in the international legal order with a strong emphasis on sovereignty, while the global South understands international law ambivalently, both as protection against arbitrariness and as a historical instrument of inequality. Forum shopping can therefore be a rational strategy in a fragmented system (Biddulph, Cooney and Zhu 2012; Rajagopal 2013; Acharya 2014; Cai 2023; DeLisle 2024). The section therefore concludes that legality is a political resource. This insight directly opens space for CLS.

7 CRITICAL LEGAL STUDIES: INTERNATIONAL LAW AS A POLITICAL FIELD

Since legality is a political resource rather than merely a normative ideal, the selectivity of state practices cannot be understood without recognising the political nature of international law. Critical Legal Studies (CLS) shows that international law is not a neutral regulator of power, but a discursive field in which power relations are translated into the language of universality (Koskenniemi 1990; Koskenniemi 2005; Kennedy 2017; Koskenniemi 2019). Koskenniemi (1990; 2005) shows that legal argumentation oscillates between "utopia", understood as universal principles or formalism, and "apology", understood as adaptation to the interests and practices of states. International law-based order (ILBO) is often presented as a universalist utopia, while rules-based international order (RBO) is presented as a pragmatic framework in which power asymmetries are more easily rationalised. This also reflects Koskenniemi's (2009) critique of International Relations as a form of new natural law.

Indeterminacy does not make law meaningless, but rather that legal meaning is often the result of dispute.¹² Legal argument is both a technique and a craft: it involves the choice of source, interpretation, framing of facts, and connection to principles. Scicluna (2021) shows that the politics of international law often takes place in 'grey areas' where formal rules are insufficient. The inclusion of RBO expands the range of arguments to standards and values, which may strengthen or weaken the discipline of international law, depending on its procedural anchoring.

Kennedy (2017) emphasises that legal discourse structures the field of political possibility. It does not remove power, but channels it into recognisable forms of argumentation. Cox's thesis¹³ that "theory is always for someone and for some purpose" (Cox 1981, 129) also applies to legal regimes. Rules on trade, investment, intellectual property, and finance are often an institutionalisation of specific assumptions about the market, property, and development. Gill (1995) therefore refers to the "constitutional" dimension of neoliberal globalisation. In

¹² This semantic openness can also be linked, to a certain extent, to Pavčnik's (2013) more general study of legal argumentation.

¹³ A similar approach can already be found in the foundations of Benko's legacy in Slovenian International Relations scholarship (1977, 187).

this context, RBO can be seen as a language that normalises preferences as ‘rules of the game’, while ILBO is a framework in which distributive conflicts can be translated into legal requirements and reform programmes.

TWAIL emphasises the colonial legacies of international law (Anghie 2005). Formal doctrines of sovereignty and contractual consent have historically coexisted with unequal treaties, mandates and trusteeships, and their weight is still preserved in customary international law. For many postcolonial states, international law is therefore ambivalent: it is both a shield against unequal negotiations and a legacy of them (Rajagopal 2013). This ambivalence now returns in disputes over climate justice, development finance and sanctions (Gilman 2015; Svetličič 2022a).

However, a critical diagnosis of power does not negate the normative potential of international law. Precisely because law needs legitimacy, powerful actors rarely reject legality outright; more often, they reinterpret it. This confirms that international law retains normative weight (Koskenniemi 2005). It also creates space for mobilisation. Weaker actors can demand compliance, initiate proceedings, form coalitions or increase the reputational costs of violation (Simmons 2009; Brunnée and Toope 2010; Brunnée and Toope 2017). Feminist and broader critical perspectives further reveal what the canon has long excluded (O’Rourke 2018): international law can function simultaneously as a shield and a sword. This ambivalence is the starting point for strategic, rather than naive, legal action by small states, which is developed in the next section.

8 STRATEGIC LEGALISM AND THE RELATIONAL CAPACITY OF SMALL STATES

In a fragmented multipolar system, the key question is what options small and medium-sized states have. Long (2022)¹⁴ shows that their influence does not stem primarily from material power, but from their relational capacity to position themselves within institutional networks, mediations and coalitions. Nexon (2019) similarly emphasises the networked nature of authority. In this sense, strategic legalism means the deliberate and selective use of international law and institutions as instruments of foreign policy, while remaining aware of power asymmetries, executive constraints and the political nature of legality. Formalised rules create at least minimal argumentative constraints even for more powerful actors, so they can be a lever for small states, not merely decoration.

Strategic legalism must be distinguished from both bare legalism, where law is treated as a value, and lawfare, where law is instrumentalised to attack an opponent. It is a reflexive use of law that recognises the overlap between legality and politics. Its purpose is not to abuse procedures, but to create predictable constraints and increase the legitimacy costs of arbitrary behaviour. It is crucial that argumentation be based on recognised sources and procedures (ILBO), even when operating in the broader discourse of RBO (Koskenniemi 2005).

¹⁴ Long successfully synthesises materialist-rationalist approaches to small states, such as those of Keohane (1969), and Udovič and Svetličič (2007), with social-psychological and social-constructivist approaches (Šabič and Brglez 2002; Thorhallsson and Wivel 2006), developing a relational conception of small states and powers in *International Relations and Comparative Foreign Policy*.

Academically, strategic legalism is situated at the intersection of international regime theory (Krasner 1982), normative entrepreneurship (Finnemore and Sikkink 1998), the judicialization of global governance (Alter 2014) and “regime shifting” (Helfer 2004). Krisch (2010) points out that the contemporary international legal order is pluralistic, making navigation between regimes a key political skill. Operationally, this involves: (i) procedural mobilisation of forums, including the ICJ, WTO, regional courts and arbitration; (ii) normative entrepreneurship, through which standards are transformed into treaty law and then customary international law; (iii) regime switching; (iv) coalition institutionalisation (Tallberg 2008; Panke 2012); and (v) legitimacy capital, understood as consistent compliance with international law as a reputational investment.

Such a strategy requires legal-diplomacy capacities for argumentation, procedural understanding, precedent analysis and alliance building. This means investing in legal services, diplomatic training and systematic monitoring of regime changes, including in the WTO, UNCLOS¹⁵ and environmental regimes. Transgovernmental and regulatory networks are an important channel. Peer-to-peer cooperation, including within the OECD,¹⁶ the EU and similar environments, enables small states to influence standards at an early stage, before they become established as global ‘rules’.

Since strategic legalism is both an instrument and a risk, the examples below illustrate typical mechanisms. The first is institutional blockage. In the WTO, a ‘rules-based trading system’ can be defended as a goal while adjudication is procedurally prevented when it would allegedly ‘create’ obligations (Office of the United States Trade Representative 2019).¹⁷ The MPIA offers a temporary appellate solution for participating WTO members, but it also demonstrates that enforcement gaps are only partially manageable without universal participation (Council of the European Union 2020).

The second is jurisdictional resistance. In the South China Sea dispute, China’s Position Paper rejects the jurisdiction of arbitration and justifies this with international law (Government of the People’s Republic of China 2014), while the tribunal documents the public position of China as a “provocation under the guise of law” (Permanent Court of Arbitration 2016).

The third is the implementation gap. The arbitration decision between Slovenia and Croatia is formally final (Permanent Court of Arbitration 2017), but the Court of Justice of the EU emphasises that the “real subject matter” is a dispute that must be resolved under international law, not EU law (Court of Justice of the European Union 2020).

The fourth is procedural pressure through provisional measures. On 26 January 2024, the ICJ indicated provisional measures in Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide in the Gaza Strip (South Africa v. Israel) (ICJ 2024a), and on 24 May 2024 it added provisional measures regarding Rafah (ICJ 2024b), creating sequential costs of non-compliance.

¹⁵ The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea.

¹⁶ The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.

¹⁷ The EU and some of its Member States responded to the blockade of the WTO Appellate Body by establishing a multilateral *interim* appeal arbitration arrangement (MPIA), based on Article 25 of the Dispute Settlement Understanding. This indicates an attempt to preserve key elements of the ILBO – proceduralised interpretation and institutional supervision – through pragmatic institutional innovation (Council of the European Union 2020).

The fifth is the enforcement gap in the individualisation of responsibility. The ICC can issue arrest warrants, but their effect is mediated by the cooperation or non-cooperation of states. In the case of Gaza, on 21 November 2024, the ICC rejected Israeli challenges to its jurisdiction and issued arrest warrants for Netanyahu and Gallant (ICC 2024). This also led to a political backlash, including US sanctions against the ICC prosecutor and judges (United States Department of State 2025). While the EU has institutionally supported the ICC (Council of the European Union 2003; European Union and International Criminal Court 2006), it has been unable or unwilling to respond to the US sanctions.

Strategic legalism thus also has risks: (i) proceedings are slow and expensive; (ii) legal mobilisation may trigger retaliatory measures; and (iii) excessive instrumentalism reduces legitimacy capital. It succeeds only by maintaining a balance between effectiveness, principledness and coalition politics.

For small states, the ILBO/RBO dilemma is not a choice between idealism and realism. ILBO remains their key protection against arbitrary power, but only if they actively use it through careful choice of forums, coalitions, consistent argumentation and investment in reputation. RBO can accelerate coalition dynamics and normative innovation, but without clear sources it increases dependence on interpretative dominance. Strategic legalism is therefore the third way for small states.¹⁸

The ISPI Report 2026 (Colombo and Magri 2026) makes this dilemma even more urgent. If deregulation, unilateralism and coalition enforcement become the dominant grammar of order, small states lose precisely the procedural density that enables them to transform weakness into legal leverage. Strategic legalism must therefore include a defensive component: preserving adjudication, treaty interpretation and institutional procedures wherever possible, while using RBO language only when it remains legally traceable, procedurally contestable and open to actors beyond the dominant coalition.

9 CONCLUDING DISCUSSION

The discussion of ILBO and RBO should conclude with a warning that RBO is neither a neutral nor a self-evident sign of order. 'Rules-based' language can serve as a politically flexible substitute for universal legal standards, creating opportunities for selectivity and double standards (Dugard 2023). Anchoring in the UN Charter and international law therefore remains a key criterion of legitimacy, especially for small and medium-sized states. Trachtenberg's (2025) historical review further demonstrates that the stability of the post-war order resulted not only from institutional liberalism, but also from political agreements on legitimate interests and power relations, as institutions are not necessarily stabilisers but also arenas of contestation. Together, these arguments support the conclusion that strategic legalism is the most realistic third way. It does not idealise international law but uses it as an argumentative and institutional constraint on arbitrary power.

¹⁸ Additional (meta-)theoretical justification for why strategic legalism is, or could be, an appropriate strategic basis for the conduct of small states in an illiberal international order is developed elsewhere (Brglez 2026b). A more empirically detailed case study of Slovenian foreign policy and the notification, or non-notification, of succession to the Austrian State Treaty is likewise provided elsewhere (Brglez 2026a). Among other things, that study substantiates why the use of strategic legalism would be particularly sensible for Slovenia as a small state.

The ISPI material and the comparative reading of recent strategic documents empirically reinforce this conclusion (Colombo and Magri 2026). They show a shift from the 2022 attempt to defend RBO as a coalition-based but still the UN Charter-compatible vocabulary towards a 2025–2026 vocabulary of sovereignty, strategic autonomy, burden-shifting, deterrence, and industrial capacity. This does not mean that ILBO has collapsed, but it does mean that its constitutional and adjudicative elements must now be defended more deliberately if ‘rules’ are not to become merely the language of the powerful.

The findings of this article confirm both introductory theses. The differences between ILBO and RBO cannot be understood abstractly, because states and international organisations interpret and apply legality strategically, with behaviour varying according to power, historical experience and internal constraints. At the same time, neither ILBO nor RBO operates outside power relations, and international law remains a structured field of political application of legality. The typology in Table 1 shows recurring combinations of discourse, institutional preferences and behaviour: (i) the liberal-hegemonic type relies on RBO and the rule of law, but often combines universalist discourse with selective use of institutions such as the WTO and ICC; (ii) normative multilateralists build on formal commitment to ILBO, but are limited by executive weakness; (iii) revisionist legalists anchor themselves in ILBO, especially the UN Charter and sovereignty, but often use law as a field of restrictive reinterpretation and resistance to control; and (iv) the pragmatic global South links legality to equality, the elimination of historical injustices and the search for the most appropriate forum, with distributive justice as the axis of legitimacy.

The mechanisms of strategic legalism show this operationally. Institutional blockage in the WTO shows how a rules-based framework can exist alongside the delegitimation of quasi-judicial dispute resolution. Jurisdictional resistance in the South China Sea arbitration demonstrates legalistic contestation of jurisdiction. The implementation gap in the Slovenia–Croatia arbitration demonstrates the limits of enforcement. Procedural pressure in *South Africa v. Israel* before the ICJ shows the sequential costs of non-compliance. Finally, the enforcement gap in the Gaza case before the ICC shows that individualised responsibility remains politically conditioned without state cooperation and may trigger backlash.

The argument therefore returns to the question of small states and powers. The choice between ILBO and RBO is not a semantic preference, but a question of access to codified procedures that at least argumentatively limit arbitrariness. Strategic legalism is the third way. It relies on codified and institutionalised international law to create minimal obstacles to the unilateral articulation of ‘rules’. It is therefore rational to invest in international legal diplomacy, coalition building and navigation between international legal regimes, while protecting one’s own legitimacy capital through consistent respect for international law.

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APPENDIX

TABLE A2: EXTENDED RECORD OF THE ATTITUDES OF COUNTRIES, INTERNATIONAL ORGANISATIONS AND INSTITUTIONS TOWARDS ILBO OR RBO

Country/organisation	Year	Document (short)	Framework	Anchor (A) – predominant	Anchor (B) – most explicit	Source
African Union	2005	Ezulwini Consensus	ILBO	Reform of global governance through (re)balancing UN institutions (especially the Security Council) + normative requirement for equality/regional representation.	Requirement: “must address the question of veto power ... and ensure full representation.”	African Union (2005)
African Union	2023	AU Assembly Decision on C-10 report (UNSC reform)	ILBO	Operationalises Common African Position (CAP): C-10 should step up engagement and mobilise support for comprehensive reform of the UN Security Council.	Requests “concise common language” in national statements at the UNGA to advance the CAP (C-10/UNSC reform).	African Union (2023)
African Union	2024	AU PAPS Press Release (Consultation with CSOs on C-10 / CAM)	ILBO	Coalition building for the CAP through consultations with African civil society; UN Security Council reform is framed as redressing a historical injustice.	Explicitly reiterates CAP: two permanent seats for Africa (with veto) + additional non-permanent seats (as part of comprehensive UN Security Council reform).	African Union (2024)
African Union	2025	AU Assembly Decision on C-10 report (UNSC reform)	ILBO	Reaffirms CAP and demands that UNSC reform be treated as a matter of legitimacy and representation (“historical injustice”).	Most explicitly: Africa as a “special case” + elimination of “historical injustice” (linked to the current UN reform process).	African Union (2025)
Brazil	2023	UN General Assembly (GA) statement (Lula)	ILBO core	The speech uses the classic multilateral/Charter framework (peace, legitimacy, reform) and links it to the development/redistribution themes of the global South.	The most explicit anchor in this speech is, as a rule, “UN / international law / peace”.	Federal Republic of Brazil (2023)
BRICS	2024	Kazan Declaration	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	Typical “global South + multipolarity”: reform of global governance, the UN as a foundation, development justice, while at the same time RBO economic anchor (WTO) and criticism of unilateral restrictive measures.	“We reaffirm our commitment to multilateralism and upholding international law, including the Purposes and Principles enshrined in the Charter of the United Nations (UN) as its indispensable cornerstone ...”	BRICS (2024)

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TABLE A2: EXTENDED RECORD OF THE ATTITUDES OF COUNTRIES, INTERNATIONAL ORGANISATIONS AND INSTITUTIONS TOWARDS ILBO OR RBO (CONTINUED)

Country/organisation	Year	Document (short)	Framework	Anchor (A) – predominant	Anchor (B) – most explicit	Source
China	2014	Position Paper (jurisdiction – South China Sea arbitration)	ILBO core	The document is legalistic: jurisdiction, consent, UNCLOS and formal sources (Article 38 of ICJ Statute) as a framework for legitimate adjudication.	In the formulations on “international law” and Article 38 of the ICJ Statute.	Government of the People’s Republic of China (2014)
China	2019	China and the United Nations: Position Paper (74th UNGA)	ILBO + RBO (WTO)	Support for multilateralism: the UN as the core of the system, the international law as the foundation of order, the WTO as the centre of the trading system; criticism of unilateralism/bullying.	“International system built around the UN, the international order underpinned by international law, and the multilateral trading system centered around the WTO.”	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People’s Republic of China (2019)
China	2025	Concept Paper on the Global Governance Initiative	ILBO	Reform of global governance with greater representation of the Global South; strengthening the effectiveness and authority of multilateral institutions.	“International system with the UN at its core... international order underpinned by international law... norms... based on the purposes and principles of the UN Charter.”	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People’s Republic of China (2025)
EU (Council)	2019	Council Conclusions 10341/19	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	The EU positions itself as the champion of multilateralism, understanding the RBO as a political framework that must be disciplined by international law and UN norms.	“We depend on a rules-based international order ... [and] must remain true to the rules and principles of the UN Charter.”	Council of the European Union (2019)
EU (European Commission)	2021	Trade Policy Review (COM(2021)66)	RBO core	It treats trade policy as a tool of “open strategic autonomy”, where stability depends on rules and viable institutions (WTO, supply chains).	“The EU has ... supported global efforts in the G20, the WTO ... to ... ensure fair and equitable access to critical goods.” (economic-institutional RBO framework; “rules-based” is also used in the document as the slogan “rules-based cooperation”)	European Commission (2021)
EU (European Commission + HRFASP)	2021	Strengthening rules-based multilateralism JOIN(2021) 3	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	The document frames the EU as a defender of “rules-based multilateralism”, capable of reforming institutions (WTO/WHO, etc.) and competing normatively in global governance.	“Firm supporters of the rules-based international order with the UN at its core.”	European Commission and High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy (2021)
EU (Council)	2022	Strategic Compass (ST 7371/22)	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	This is an operational document: toolboxes, resilience, hybrid/cyber; normatively linked to the defence of order and the prohibition of coercion.	“Rules-based international order, based on ... universal values and international law ... has come under strong questioning ...”	Council of the European Union (2022)

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TABLE A2: EXTENDED RECORD OF THE ATTITUDES OF COUNTRIES, INTERNATIONAL ORGANISATIONS AND INSTITUTIONS TOWARDS ILBO OR RBO (CONTINUED)

Country/organisation	Year	Document (short)	Framework	Anchor (A) - predominant	Anchor (B) - most explicit	Source
France	2022	National Strategic Review	ILBO core	Normative emphasis: "multilateralism + rule of law"; additionally draws attention to "lawfare" as the instrumentalisation of law/norms.	"International order based on multilateralism and the rule of law ..."	French Republic (2022)
France	2024	Macron (Rio) – global governance	ILBO core	The speech focuses on reforming global governance and the universality of rules without double standards.	" <i>Nous sommes tous signataires de la Charte des Nations Unies.</i> "	Macron (2024)
G7	2024	Apulia Leaders' Communiqué	RBO core	The communiqué uses "rules-based" primarily as an economic/coalition framework: WTO, rule reforms, enforceability through national legal systems and sanctioning instruments.	"Commitment to the rules-based ... multilateral trading system, with the WTO at its core."	Group of Seven (2024)
G77 + China	2025	Ministerial Declaration	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	The declaration is ILBO-heavy (UN Charter/ILBO, justice, development), but it also has a clear RBO economic layer (WTO "rules-based multilateral trading system").	"Full respect for ... the Charter of the United Nations and international law."	Group of 77 and China (2025)
Germany	2021	Coalition Treaty 2021–2025	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	The coalition agreement links the strengthening of the UN with a "rules-based international order" and multilateral institutional reform.	"Strengthening of the United Nations and a rules-based international order."	Federal Republic of Germany (2021a)
Germany	2021	International law and cyberspace (position paper)	ILBO core	The document operationalises ILBO: application of IHL principles (distinction, proportionality, precaution) and restrictions on countermeasures.	"International law as it stands provides binding guidance ..." (the text elaborates International Humanitarian Law standards for cyberspace)	Federal Republic of Germany (2021b)
Germany	2023	National Security Strategy	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	The security-political order is explicitly "UN Charter + international law", while the economic order is described as "rules-based".	It advocates: "... order based on international law, the United Nations Charter ..." and "promote the ... rules-based order"	Federal Republic of Germany (2023)
India	2024	Special Committee on the Charter	ILBO core	The document builds on Charter legalism: peaceful dispute resolution, the role of the ICJ, and respect for Charter procedures.	Explicit reference usually in sentences with "UN Charter / Article 2(3) / Article 33."	Permanent Mission of India to the United Nations (2024a)
India	2024	Charter Committee statement	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	India subordinates the rules-based framework of the UN Charter/ILBO as a universal foundation; "RBO" is legitimate only if it is Charter-based.	"Strengthening a rules-based international order based on the UN Charter and international law ..."	Permanent Mission of India to the United Nations (2024b)
Indonesia	2024	UNGA General Debate	ILBO core	The speech generally justifies multilateralism, humanitarian standards and the legitimacy of solutions through the UN.	Most explicitly, as a rule, "international law / UN Charter".	Republic of Indonesia (2024)
Kenya	2024	UNGA statement	ILBO core	Kenya links stability to the consistent application of Charter norms and international law, with an emphasis on legitimacy and predictability.	"The only guarantee for stability is strict adherence to the UN Charter and the consistent application of international law ..."	Republic of Kenya (2024)

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TABLE A2: EXTENDED RECORD OF THE ATTITUDES OF COUNTRIES, INTERNATIONAL ORGANISATIONS AND INSTITUTIONS TOWARDS ILBO OR RBO (CONTINUED)

Country/organisation	Year	Document (short)	Framework	Anchor (A) - predominant	Anchor (B) - most explicit	Source
NAM	2024	Statement by Indonesia on behalf of NAM	ILBO + criticism of RBO	NAM explicitly rejects unilateral practices "under the guise" of RBO and establishes the Charter/ILBO as the sole universal framework.	"Reject ... under the guise of a so-called 'rules-based international order' ... reaffirm ... the Charter of the United Nations ... and international law."	Non-Aligned Movement (2024)
NATO	2022	Strategic Concept	Mixed (ILBO+RBO)	It frames strategic competition as a defence of the "open" order and legitimises the strengthening of deterrence and partnerships as safeguards against coercion.	"We will uphold the rules-based international order, including the principles of the UN Charter."	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (2022)
Russia	2022	Putin's Letter to UN Security Council (24 Feb 2022)	ILBO core	The document is formally Charter-procedural: it refers to self-defence and requests distribution to the UN Security Council.	"Measures taken in accordance with Article 51 of the Charter of the United Nations in exercise of the right of self-defence ..."	United Nations Security Council (2022)
Russia	2023	Foreign Policy Concept	ILBO + criticism of RBO	The concept builds on ILBO as a foundation, while describing RBO as a project that undermines the legal system and allows for arbitrary interpretations.	"Promotion of a rules-based world order is fraught with the destruction of the international legal system ..."	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation (2023)
Russia	2023	Lavrov article (5 May 2023)	ILBO + criticism of RBO	The core issue is the delegitimation of RBO as a "replacement" for the Charter/ILBO and the question of "who sets the rules".	"Replace international law and the UN Charter with some 'rules-based international order' ..."	Lavrov (2023)
Slovenia	2019	Resolution on the National Security Strategy of the Republic of Slovenia	ILBO	National security is enshrined in the constitutional order, the rule of law and respect for international obligations; the classification of threats and responses is based on international commitments and regimes.	"We respect the principles of international law and the rights and obligations ... assumed under international treaties."	Republic of Slovenia (2019)
Slovenia	2021	Foreign Policy Strategy of the Republic of Slovenia	ILBO	Multilateral action is the central mechanism for addressing common challenges, with the UN at its core; Slovenia emphasises peaceful dispute resolution and support for international courts.	"Effective multilateral cooperation ... respect for international law, drawing on the UN Charter ... multilateral engagement, with the UN at its core."	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Slovenia (2021)
Slovenia	2024	Foreign Policy Strategy of the Republic of Slovenia	Mixed (ILBO-predominant)	The strategy grounds Slovenia's foreign policy in effective multilateralism, sovereign equality, solidarity and respect for international law, with the UN at its core; it also notes the erosion of multilateralism and the RBO in a security-oriented EU/NATO context.	"Effective multilateral cooperation ... respect for international law, drawing on the UN Charter" + "erosion of multilateralism and the rules-based world order."	Ministry of Foreign and European Affairs of the Republic of Slovenia (2024)
South Africa	2024	UNGA statement	ILBO core	The speech justifies multilateralism, sovereign equality and the legitimacy of solutions through the UN.	The most explicit anchor is the typical "Charter / international law" formulation.	Republic of South Africa (2024)

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TABLE A2: EXTENDED RECORD OF THE ATTITUDES OF COUNTRIES, INTERNATIONAL ORGANISATIONS AND INSTITUTIONS TOWARDS ILBO OR RBO (CONTINUED)

Country/organisation	Year	Document (short)	Framework	Anchor (A) - predominant	Anchor (B) - most explicit	Source
South Africa	2026	Statement to UNSC (Venezuela)	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	The ILBO core (sovereign equality, prohibition of force, peaceful settlement of disputes) is enhanced by the explicit formula "rules-based ... based on international law".	"We all benefit from a rules-based international order based on international law."	Republic of South Africa (2026)
UK	2023	Integrated Review Refresh	Mixed (ILBO↔RBO)	The UK frames competition as a battle for "rules/norms/institutions", but explicitly states that defending the post-Cold War RBO alone is no longer sufficient.	It concludes: "... respect for the ... UN Charter and international law" + "defending the post-Cold War 'rules-based international system' are no longer sufficient ..."	HM Government (2023)
UK	2025	House of Lords debate	RBO core	Parliamentary discourse legitimises a modernised RBO as the basis for international responsibility and political community.	"Support to a modernised rules-based international order ..."	House of Lords (2025)
US	2019	Report on the WTO Appellate Body	RBO (trade)	"Rules-based" is used as a justification for reforming/limiting judicial interpretation and "unwritten obligations".	"A critically important component of maintaining confidence in a rules-based trading system... [is] ... ensuring that ... bodies... do not impose obligations that are not contained in the WTO Agreements."	Office of the United States Trade Representative (2019)
US	2022	National Security Strategy	Mixed (RBO + ILBO)	The NSS legitimises the "rules-based order" as the broad desire of most countries, while the links this to the fundamental principles of the UN and international law.	"The vast majority of countries want a stable and open rules-based order ..." and "uphold the ... principles of the United Nations, including respect for international law."	The White House (2022)
US	2025	National Security Strategy	RBO (critical-defensive)	The document explicitly problematises the "so-called rules-based international order" as a tool/ideology of opponents and places it in a competitive framework.	"Their vision for a future global order is the so-called 'rules-based international order' ..."	The White House (2025)
US	2026	National Defence Strategy	No ILBO/RBO; it is "peace through strength"	The dominant logic is that of geostrategic coercion/deterrence ("peace through strength"), not a normative typology of order.	"This is how we will set conditions for lasting peace through strength ..."	United States Department of War (2026)

Source: author's own elaboration, based on the documents listed in the final column and the accompanying Zenodo dataset (Brglez 2026c).

NA MEDNARODNEM PRAVU ALI NA PRAVILIH UTEMELJEN MEDNARODNI RED? POLITIKA MEDNARODNEGA PRAVA V PRIMERJALNI PERSPEKTIVI

Članek analizira sodobno izpodbijanje globalnega reda z razlikovanjem med redom, utemeljenim na mednarodnem pravu (ILBO), in mednarodnim redom, utemeljenim na pravilih (RBO). Zagovarja tezo, da so polikrize po letu 2008 in multipolarizacija mednarodne skupnosti oslabile institucionalno učinkovitost liberalnega mednarodnega reda (LIO) ter ponovno odprle vprašanje legitimne legalnosti. Primerja ILBO, ki je zasidran v doktrini pravnih virov, Ustanovni listini Združenih narodov in metodah tolmačenja mednarodnega prava, z RBO kot širšim in bolj politično interpretativnim okvirom. Primerjava je organizirana okrog treh meril: normativne strukture, institucionalne infrastrukture in izvrševanja. Članek nato v odnosu do problematike razvije primerjalno tipologijo državnih strategij ter se opre na kritične pravne študije, da bi tudi mednarodno pravo razumel kot polje političnega boja. Sklepno razvije strateški legalizem kot način, s katerim lahko male države mednarodno pravo uporabljajo relacijsko pri upravljanju asimetrij moči v mednarodni skupnosti.

Ključne besede: liberalni mednarodni red (LIO); mednarodni red, utemeljen na pravilih (RBO); primerjalna politika; red, utemeljen na mednarodnem pravu (ILBO); strateški legalizem.